

IPSAS AND FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN PUBLIC SECTOR ENTITIES IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: The study examined the extent to which the adoption of IPSAS leads to better financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra state. Descriptive cross-sectional survey research design was utilized in the study. The population of the study was made up of 244 full-time staff of selected public organisations in Awka Metropolis from which a sample size of 152 respondents were chosen. In this study, primary data were collected using self-administered questionnaires composed of closed-ended questions. The study's descriptive statistical analysis utilized measures such as mean, frequency counts, and percentages. The hypothesis was tested using the Spearman Ranked Order Correlation Coefficient, which was calculated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25. The findings revealed that: the adoption of IPSAS significantly leads to better financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra State ($\rho = 0.901$, $p\text{-value} < 0.000$). In conclusion, as public organizations continue to adopt these standards, it is likely that they will experience further improvements in their operational efficiency and accountability, ultimately benefiting the broader public sector domain in Nigeria.

Key words: IPSAS, Financial management practices and Public sector entities

Introduction

The public sector plays an essential function inside the socio-economic development of any state, serving because the primary mechanism for delivering public goods and services, handling public sources, and implementing rules for sustainable boom. In Nigeria, the public area is a essential component of the financial system, encompassing various authorities ministries, departments, and groups at federal, country, and local stages, but, one of the great challenges facing the Nigerian public quarter has been the problem of transparency, responsibility, and the efficient management of public price range (Abatcha, 2024). The implementation of robust accounting standards is vital for reinforcing those factors, and the adoption of worldwide Public area Accounting standards (IPSAS) represents a important step closer to reaching this goal (Ezejiofor, Okolocha & Ofurum, 2020).IPSAS are designed to improve the quality of general-purpose financial reporting by public sector entities, thereby increasing transparency and accountability (Zibaghafa & Okpolosa, 2024). The standards are issued by the International Public Sector Accounting Standards Board (IPSASB) and are intended to be applied by entities that prepare financial statements in accordance with accrual-based accounting. The adoption of IPSAS is expected to lead to better financial management practices, enhance the comparability of

financial statements, and facilitate better decision-making processes (Abatcha, 2024). In Nigeria, particularly in Anambra State, the adoption of IPSAS is seen as a significant move towards improving public sector financial management and aligning with international best practices.

In Nigeria, the adoption of IPSAS has been driven by the need to improve public sector financial management and align with international best practices (Ezejiofor, Okolocha & Ofurum, 2020). The Federal Executive Council approved the adoption of IPSAS in 2010, and since then, various government entities have been working towards full compliance. The adoption of IPSAS has a profound impact on the public sector, influencing various aspects of financial management and reporting (Adedeji, 2024). By requiring public sector entities to prepare financial statements on an accrual basis, IPSAS provides a more comprehensive and accurate view of their financial position and performance. This increased transparency helps to build trust among stakeholders, including citizens, investors, and international partners, and promotes better governance (Zibaghafa & Chukwu, 2024).

Effective public sector is one which operates with the highest standards of financial transparency, accountability, and efficiency. The adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) helps to ensure that all financial statements are prepared on an accrual basis, providing a comprehensive and accurate representation of the financial position and performance of public sector entities (Ezejiofor, Okolocha & Ofurum, 2020). This level of financial reporting would ordinarily enable stakeholders, including government officials, citizens, investors, and international partners, to make informed decisions based on reliable and comparable financial information. Additionally, the adherence to IPSAS would promote better financial management practices, reduce instances of corruption and mismanagement, and enhance the overall governance and delivery of public services (Abatcha, 2024).

In reality, however, the implementation of IPSAS in Nigeria's public sector, including Anambra State, has faced significant challenges. Despite the Federal Executive Council's approval of IPSAS adoption in 2010, many public sector entities have struggled with full compliance. Issues such as inadequate training and capacity building for personnel, outdated financial systems and processes, and resistance to change have hindered the effective implementation of these standards (Zibaghafa & Okpolosa, 2024). Consequently, financial statements in many public sector entities are still prepared on a near cash basis, lacking the comprehensive and accurate information provided by accrual accounting. This gap between the ideal and actual implementation of IPSAS results in financial reports that are less transparent, less reliable, and not comparable across different entities and jurisdictions (Alkhabbaz & Suresh, 2023).

This study is a further work that follows from existing researches conducted by Abatcha (2024); Zibaghafa and Okpolosa (2024); Okpara, Eke and Ajobor (2023) and likes. However, a gap in literature which was spotted among the existing studies is that they did not establish whether a link exists between IPSAS adoption and the comparability of financial statements among public sector entities in Anambra state.

The main objective of the study is to examine the influence of international public sector accounting standard in public sector in Anambra state. The specific objective is to examine the extent to which the adoption of IPSAS leads to better financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra state.

Review of Related Literature

International Public Sector Accounting Standards

International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) are a comprehensive set of accounting standards developed to enhance the quality, consistency, and transparency of financial reporting within the public sector globally (Ojeh & Eze, 2023). These standards are formulated by the International Public Sector Accounting Standards Board (IPSASB), which operates under the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC). IPSAS

aims to address the unique accounting and financial reporting needs of public sector entities, which differ significantly from those of the private sector due to their focus on public service rather than profit generation (Zibaghafa & Okpolosa, 2024). By establishing a common framework for accounting in the public sector, IPSAS seeks to ensure that financial statements produced by governments and public sector entities are comparable, transparent, and useful for stakeholders, including citizens, government officials, and international organizations (Oluwayemisi, Alade, Awe & Akinyosoye, 2024).

The importance of IPSAS lies in its potential to improve governance and accountability within the public sector (Okpara, Eke & Ajobor, 2023). In many countries, public sector financial management has historically been plagued by inconsistencies, lack of transparency, and poor financial reporting practices. IPSAS provides a standardized approach to financial reporting that helps to rectify these issues by requiring entities to adhere to principles that promote accuracy, reliability, and relevance in their financial statements. This standardization is particularly crucial for countries seeking to improve their financial management practices, attract investment, and gain the confidence of international donors and financial institutions. By adopting IPSAS, governments can demonstrate their commitment to sound financial governance and enhance the trust of citizens and other stakeholders in public financial management (Okpara, Eke & Ajobor, 2023).

Furthermore, IPSAS plays a critical role in enabling better decision-making in the public sector. Accurate and transparent financial information is essential for making informed policy decisions, allocating resources effectively, and assessing the financial sustainability of government programs (Oluwayemisi, Alade, Awe & Akinyosoye, 2024). IPSAS helps to ensure that the financial statements of public sector entities provide a true and fair view of their financial position and performance, which, in turn, supports sound decision-making processes (Zibaghafa & Okpolosa, 2024). Additionally, IPSAS facilitates the comparability of financial information across different jurisdictions and over time, enabling governments and international organizations to assess and compare the financial health and performance of public sector entities globally.

Financial Management Practices

Financial management practices refer to the systematic strategies, processes, and procedures employed by organizations to manage their financial resources in an effective and efficient manner (Dorfleitner & Nguyen, 2024). These practices encompass a broad range of activities, including budgeting, financial planning, accounting, financial reporting, internal controls, and investment management. The primary objective of financial management practices is to ensure that an organization's financial resources are utilized optimally to achieve its strategic goals and objectives while maintaining financial stability and sustainability (Balogun & Fatogun, 2022).

Effective financial management practices are critical to the success of any organization, whether in the public or private sector (Hussaini, 2024). These practices provide the foundation for making informed financial decisions, managing risks, and ensuring accountability for the use of financial resources. For instance, budgeting is a fundamental financial management practice that involves forecasting revenues and expenditures, setting financial goals, and allocating resources accordingly. A well-prepared budget serves as a roadmap for an organization, guiding its financial activities and ensuring that resources are directed toward priority areas.

In addition to budgeting, financial management practices include robust financial planning and analysis. This involves assessing an organization's current financial position, projecting future financial performance, and evaluating various financial scenarios to support strategic decision-making. Financial planning helps organizations anticipate potential challenges, identify opportunities for growth, and make adjustments to their

financial strategies as needed. It also plays a crucial role in ensuring that an organization remains financially resilient in the face of economic uncertainties and other external pressures. Another key aspect of financial management practices is the establishment of strong internal controls and governance mechanisms (Dorfleitner & Nguyen, 2024). These controls are designed to safeguard an organization's assets, prevent fraud and errors, and ensure compliance with financial regulations and standards. Effective internal controls include measures such as segregation of duties, regular financial audits, and the implementation of robust financial policies and procedures. By maintaining a high standard of financial governance, organizations can enhance their credibility and build trust with stakeholders, including investors, donors, and regulatory authorities.

Finally, financial management practices also encompass investment management, which involves the prudent allocation of financial resources to generate returns and support the long-term financial health of the organization. This includes decisions related to capital investments, asset management, and the management of financial risks through diversification and hedging strategies. Sound investment management is essential for organizations seeking to grow their financial assets and ensure their sustainability over the long term.

Empirical Review

Abatcha (2024) investigated the effect of adopting International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on the quality of financial reports in the public sector of Borno State. Secondary data was collected from 17 Ministries in the state. The Theory of isomorphism was used as the study's framework. The study adopted a descriptive survey design, and the collected data underwent a completeness check, followed by summarization, coding, and tabulation using SPSS version 20. Descriptive statistics were applied to describe the study variables, while paired-sample t-tests were conducted to identify any significant differences between old accounting standards and assess the quality scores. Findings reveal that IPSAS-based reports in Borno State scored higher in relevance and comparability compared to old standards-based reports, but had lower scores in faithful representation and understandability. The study recommends a cautious transition to accrual basis IPSAS standards, granting more autonomy for financial management reforms, and utilizing past financial data for a reality check in budgeting.

Hussaini (2024) evaluated the perceived impact of IPSAS adoption on ethical behavior in public monetary management of the North-eastern States of Nigeria. The look at explores the impact of adopting IPSAS on ethical conduct and economic management practices. A primary research technique turned into hired using a questionnaire to gather records on perceived adoption, ethical behavior, financial control, perceived IPSAS management, and implementation advantages. A multi-level sampling method become used to choose respondents from the North-jap states of Nigeria. facts analysis worried descriptive and inferential records, such as ANOVA and correlation analysis, carried out using SPSS. through a mixed-method approach, information changed into amassed the use of questionnaires and analyzed the usage of descriptive and inferential facts. Findings indicate a usually tremendous perception of IPSAS adoption throughout demographic groups, with versions in belief based on factors such as age, training level, and years of enjoy. ANOVA consequences monitor sizable differences in perceived adoption, ethical behavior, financial control, perceived IPSAS control and implementation blessings a number of the North-japanese states. The correlation matrix indicates strong tremendous correlations between perceived adoption, moral conduct, and implementation benefits, highlighting the ability benefits of IPSAS adoption. The look at indicates that efforts to beautify IPSAS adoption and improve financial management practices should positively effect ethical conduct and implementation benefits inside the vicinity. Similarly research and focused interventions are endorsed to address specific demanding situations and maximize the blessings of IPSAS adoption in North-jap Nigeria. Okpara, Eke, and Ajobor (2023) investigated the impact of worldwide Public region Accounting requirements (IPSAS) on monetary reporting in

Edo kingdom, Nigeria. The specific goals were to analyze the impact of IPSAS on the disclosure of economic records, transparency and responsibility in monetary reporting, and the comparability of economic reporting inside the public region in Edo country. A survey layout approach changed into hired, and questionnaires were administered to 208 chartered accountants working in Ministries and corporations under the Edo kingdom authorities. Descriptive and inferential information had been used to investigate the facts, and Pearson Chi-square became hired to check the have a look at's hypotheses. The findings discovered that IPSAS has a huge effect at the disclosure of economic facts, transparency, and responsibility in public zone monetary reporting in Edo kingdom. Moreover, it turned into determined that IPSAS appreciably influences the comparability of economic reviews. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that IPSAS drastically affects public area monetary reporting in Edo country, Nigeria. Alkhabbaz and Suresh (2023) investigate the impact of adopting International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on the comparability of financial reports in the public sector of India. To achieve this, both primary and secondary sources of data were used. A well-designed questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale was employed to collect primary data from accounts department employees of Public Sector Enterprises (PSEs) in India. One hundred questionnaires were distributed, and 75 were returned, which formed the sample size at a 5% level of significance. SPSS software was employed to analyze the collected data, and Spearman's correlation test was used for testing the hypothesis. The study found that the adoption of IPSAS has a significantly positive impact on the comparability of financial reports in the public sector of India, as it increases this level.

Olaru (2023) examined the practical improvement in the quality of financial reporting in Romanian public institutions after implementing IPSAS. A questionnaire addressed to accounting professionals in the local public administration was used, with 164 respondents participating. A linear regression analysis method was employed to examine the relationship between the implementation of IPSAS and the quality of financial reporting in Romanian public institutions. The introduction of IPSAS was found to be significantly positively related to the quality of financial reporting in Romanian public institutions. The findings recommend that regulators take appropriate measures to ensure compliance by those responsible for preparing financial statements of public sector entities.

Tawiah (2023) investigated the effect of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on corruption in developing countries. The System Generalised Method of Moments was employed on a sample of 77 developing countries between 2005 and 2017. The study found that IPSAS is negatively and significantly associated with corruption, suggesting that the adoption of IPSAS helps control corruption in developing countries. These results held even after accounting for IPSAS experience and the adoption of other international accounting standards. Further analyses revealed that the negative impact of IPSAS on corruption is more pronounced in countries that have fully adopted the accrual-based IPSAS. This study provides evidence to policymakers on why developing countries should adopt IPSAS, especially in the fight against corruption.

Ngwayi and Alabede (2022) examined the effect of public region economic reporting attributes on public responsibility at the subnational degree, specializing in Taraba country, Nigeria. facts was amassed the usage of a questionnaire administered to a random pattern of accounting and auditing group of workers throughout all Taraba nation ministries. Pearson's correlation coefficient and multiple regression evaluation had been used to determine the path and importance of the relationship among the variables and to check the hypotheses. The findings found out a statistically big high quality impact of relevance, reliability, and comparison of public quarter economic reporting attributes on responsibility in Taraba kingdom. However, the statistical evidence did no longer establish a good sized relationship between understandability and timeliness of public sector economic reporting attributes and accountability. The look at concluded that to entrench more accountability at the subnational level in Nigeria, especially in Taraba nation, policymakers and accounting operators have to institute a method that makes public area financial reviews greater applicable, dependable, and similar. Al-Kharabsheh (2021) tested the effect of adopting international Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on financial performance in the Jordanian public sector, aiming to reform its accounting gadget to control public

money. The have a look at is extensive due to its timing in the course of Jordan's difficult economic and monetary conditions and the authorities' attention of IPSAS adoption as an entrepreneurial circulates. Descriptive and inferential methods had been implemented for statistics evaluation. A questionnaire became designed to acquire records from accountants inside the Ministry of Finance and analyzed using SPSS. One key result is that adopting IPSAS on an accrual foundation complements transparency, credibility, reliability, and complete disclosure of monetary statements. Egolum and Ndum (2021) tested the effect of IPSAS on the monetary reporting fine of the Anambra state public zone. The look at centered on three goals: accountability, transparency, and corruption reduction. A survey studies layout and primary information were used, with questionnaires distributed to workforce within the Anambra nation Ministry of Finance. The population comprised all 127 body of workers participants, and the researcher used the complete populace for the study. The instrument's validity was confirmed, and the internal consistency became confirmed the usage of Cronbach's Alpha, with a coefficient value of 0.eighty two. Data have been analyzed using frequency counts, suggest rankings, and general deviation, with hypotheses tested the usage of the Chi-rectangular statistical tool with SPSS version 20.0 at a five% significance degree. The have a look at found out that IPSAS adoption ends in increased accountability, improved transparency, and reduced corruption among public officials. The researchers propose that the Nigerian government offer the necessary support for the overall implementation and sustenance of IPSAS in the public sector.

Methodology

Research Design

For this study, a descriptive cross-sectional survey research design was utilized. This design was chosen because it aligns with the researcher's goal to describe the characteristics of specific groups, estimate the proportion of individuals with certain traits, and make predictions. By adopting this design, the study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the subjects under investigation, allowing for an in-depth exploration of their characteristics and behaviors at a single point in time. This approach ensures that the research objectives are met through a structured and methodical process.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised all the full-time staff of the three selected public organisations in Awka Metropolis. The three purposively selected public organisations are Anambra Broadcasting Service (ABS), Anambra State Housing Development Corporation, and Anambra State Water Corporation, all in Awka. The population target of the study is given below in **Table 3.1**.

Table 1 Population of the Study

Name of Organisation	Number of Staff
1. Anambra Broadcasting Service, Awka (ABS)	74
2. Anambra State Housing Development Corporation (ASH)	87
3. Anambra State Water Corporation (ASW)	83
Total	244

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Sample Size Determination

From a total population of 244, the sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's (1964) formula for sample size determination in finite populations. According to Yamane (1964), the sample size for a finite population is calculated using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(\epsilon)^2}$$

Where:

n - Sample size

N - Population size

e - The level of precision, sometimes called sampling error, is the range in which the true value of the population is estimated to be.

1 - Constant

Therefore;

Substituting the values in the formula where $e = 5\%$ we have:

$$N = 244$$

$$e = 0.05$$

$$n = ?$$

$$n = \frac{244}{1+244(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{244}{1+244(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{244}{1+0.61}$$

$$n = \frac{244}{1.61}$$

$$n = 151.55$$

Approximately, $n = 152$

The study uses a sample size of one hundred and fifty-two (152). The total sample was rationed into three strata for the three selected organisations using the formula below:

$$\text{Stratum size} = \frac{\text{number of staff in each company}}{\text{total population target}} \times \text{study sample size}$$

$$\text{Stratum Size for ABS} = \frac{74}{244} \times 152 = 46$$

$$\text{Stratum Size for ASW} = \frac{87}{244} \times 152 = 54$$

$$\text{Stratum Size for ASH} = \frac{83}{244} \times 152 = 52$$

Table 2: Distribution of the Sample Size of the Study

Name of Organisation	Strata Size
1. Anambra Broadcasting Service, Awka (ABS)	46
2. Anambra State Housing Development Corporation (ASH)	54
3. Anambra State Water Corporation (ASW)	54
Total	152

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2023

Method of Data Collection

In this study, primary data were collected using self-administered questionnaires composed of closed-ended questions. The questionnaire was carefully designed with a 5-point Likert scale to assess various constructs. This format provided respondents with the convenience to complete the survey at their own pace, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of their answers. The choice to use a questionnaire was based on its ability to standardize data collection, ensuring that all participants received the same questions in a consistent format. This structured approach enabled efficient and cost-effective data collection from a sample that represents the broader population, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the entire population.

Measurement of Variables

The variables of the study were measured using primary data. Each of the responses was ranked using the Likert scale system of 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, 1 = strongly disagree. The content scope includes an analysis of how the adoption of IPSAS impacts financial management practices, enhances the comparability of financial statements, and facilitates better decision-making processes. Each of the scales (adoption of IPSAS, financial management practices, enhances the comparability of financial statements, and facilitates better decision-making processes) contain 4 items ranked using 5-point Likert system. Below is a table representing the measurement of the variables in the study:

Table 3. Measurement of Variable

Variable	Number of Items	Measurement Scale
Adoption of IPSAS	4	5-point Likert scale
Financial Management Practices	4	5-point Likert scale
Enhances the Comparability of Financial Statements	4	5-point Likert scale
Facilitates Better Decision-Making Processes	4	5-point Likert scale

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

Method of Data Analysis

The study's descriptive statistical analysis utilized measures such as mean, frequency counts, and percentages. These statistical methods were chosen for their simplicity and ease of interpretation. In contrast, the inferential statistical analysis aimed to assess the study's null hypotheses. To achieve this, the researcher employed the Spearman Ranked Order Correlation Coefficient, which was calculated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25.

Decision Rule

The hypotheses testing were carried out with a significance level of 5%. If the p-value of the test is higher than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, if the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Data Analysis

Response Rate of the Questionnaire

Among the 152 questionnaires that were distributed, 137 were returned fully completed, accounting for 90.13% of the total distributed. Additionally, 8 questionnaires (5.26%) were incorrectly filled out, and 7 questionnaires were not returned, representing 7.14% of the total questionnaires given to respondents. Given the achieved response rate of at least 70%, the study continued and is suitable for inferential analysis. Please, refer to Table 4.1 for a summarized presentation of these statistics.

Table 1: Response Rate

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Well Filled in Questionnaires	137	90.13
Wrongly-Filled in Questionnaires	8	5.26
Unreturned Questionnaires	7	4.61
Total	152	100

Source: Survey Findings, 2024

Analysis of Mean Scores for the Variables

The questionnaire items that measured the variables of study; it is pertinent to note the following: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree.

Table 4 Presentation of Mean Scores for the Variables: Adoption of IPSAS

S/N	Statements About the Research Variable	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean
1	The adoption of IPSAS has improved the transparency of financial reporting in our organization.	4	57	0	76	0	2.92
2	IPSAS adoption has increased the accuracy of financial statements in our public sector entity.	23	68	0	46	0	3.5
3	Implementing IPSAS has been beneficial for aligning our financial reporting with international standards.	23	41	0	73	0	3.10
4	Adopting IPSAS has enhanced accountability in our public sector financial management	6	58	0	73	0	2.98

Source: Survey Findings, 2024

In Table 4, the mean scores for various statements regarding the adoption of the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) are presented. Each statement reflects a different dimension of how IPSAS is perceived to affect financial practices within organizations.

The first statement, which posits that the adoption of IPSAS has improved the transparency of financial reporting, received a mean score of 2.92. This score indicates a generally neutral to slightly positive perception among respondents, particularly given that a significant majority (57) chose "Agree" while 76 responded "Disagree." The low proportion of strong agreement and disagreement suggests mixed feelings about the impact of IPSAS on transparency.

The second statement assesses whether IPSAS adoption has increased the accuracy of financial statements. With a mean score of 3.5, this statement garnered the highest level of agreement among respondents, as evidenced by 23 selecting "Strongly Agree" and 68 opting for "Agree." The responses indicate a more robust belief that IPSAS positively influences financial accuracy within public sector entities.

The third statement considers whether implementing IPSAS has been beneficial for aligning financial reporting with international standards. This statement received a mean score of 3.10, showing a moderately positive view. Here, the responses were more evenly distributed, with notable agreement (23 "Strongly Agree" and 41 "Agree"), yet a significant number (73) still disagreed, highlighting a divide in perceptions regarding alignment with international standards.

Lastly, the statement regarding the enhancement of accountability through IPSAS adoption produced a mean score of 2.98. Similar to the first statement, it indicates a moderate level of agreement, with 6 respondents strongly agreeing and a majority (58) agreeing. However, the higher count of those disagreeing (73) indicates a notable skepticism about whether IPSAS truly fosters greater accountability in public sector financial management.

Table 5: Presentation of Mean Scores for the Variable: Financial Management Practices

S/N	Statements About the Research Variable	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean
5	The adoption of IPSAS has led to better financial planning in our organization.	1	136	0	0	0	4.01
6	IPSAS adoption has improved the efficiency of financial controls within our public sector entity.	17	47	0	73	0	3.06
7	With IPSAS, our organization has achieved greater accuracy in financial forecasting.	6	76	0	55	0	3.24
8	The adoption of IPSAS has led to more responsible financial management practices in our organization.	33	52	2	50	0	3.50

Source: Survey Findings, 2024

Table 5 presents the mean scores for various statements regarding financial management practices in relation to the adoption of the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS). Each statement provides insight into how IPSAS is perceived to influence financial management within organizations.

The first statement highlights the belief that IPSAS adoption has led to better financial planning in the organization. With a mean score of 4.01, this statement received overwhelming support, as indicated by the 136 respondents who agreed. The near absence of disagreement suggests a strong consensus among participants that IPSAS has positively impacted their financial planning processes.

The second statement focuses on the efficiency of financial controls post-IPSAS adoption. It recorded a mean score of 3.06, reflecting a more mixed perspective. While 17 respondents strongly agreed and 47 agreed, a substantial number (73) disagreed, indicating that opinions on the improvement of financial controls are divided. This disparity suggests that while some respondents see benefits in efficiency, others may not perceive significant changes.

The third statement assesses the impact of IPSAS on the accuracy of financial forecasting. It garnered a mean score of 3.24, which indicates a generally favorable view, albeit with some skepticism. The responses included 6 strong agreements and a majority of 76 in favor, yet 55 respondents disagreed. This suggests that while many believe IPSAS has enhanced forecasting accuracy, a significant portion still questions its effectiveness in this area.

The final statement evaluates whether IPSAS adoption has led to more responsible financial management practices. With a mean score of 3.50, this statement received notable support, particularly with 33 respondents strongly agreeing and 52 agreeing. However, the presence of 50 disagreements indicates that opinions remain somewhat divided, suggesting that while many recognize improvements in financial responsibility, and others may not share this view.

Test of Hypothesis

From which indicate the item-by-item analysis of the research variables of the study, the data for the test of hypotheses were collected and analysed using Spearman Ranked Order Correlation Coefficient.

For the test of the first hypothesis, the under-stated null hypothesis is deployed:

H01: The adoption of IPSAS does not significantly lead to better financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra state.

The test of the hypothesis has the following outputs.

Table 6; Correlation Result for Hypothesis I

			Financial management practices
		Correlation Coefficient	.901**
Spearman's rho	IPSAS	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	137

Source: Survey Findings, 2024

The results presented in Table 6 focus on testing the hypothesis regarding the influence of the adoption of the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra State. The correlation coefficient, Spearman's rho = 0.901, indicates a very strong positive relationship between IPSAS adoption and financial management practices. Additionally, the p-value of 0.000 confirms that this correlation is statistically significant. With a sample size of 137, the findings suggest that changes in IPSAS adoption significantly influence financial management practices within the public sector.

Decision

Given that the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H01) is rejected, while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This leads to the conclusion that the adoption of IPSAS significantly leads to better financial management practices among public sector entities in Anambra State ($\rho = 0.901$, $p\text{-value} < 0.000$).

Discussion of Findings

The findings regarding the positive influence of IPSAS on financial management practices are well-supported by various studies in the empirical review. For instance, Mohammed et al. (2022) highlighted a positive impact of IPSAS on financial management and accountability, indicating that the adoption of these standards fosters better governance. Similarly, Hussaini (2024) found significant differences in perceived financial management practices among states that adopted IPSAS, underscoring a broader acceptance of the standards' benefits. The strong correlation coefficient observed in the current study aligns with these findings, suggesting that public sector entities in Anambra State can achieve improved financial management through IPSAS implementation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

An effective public sector operates with the best standards of economic transparency, responsibility, and performance. The adopting international Public sector accounting requirements (IPSAS) guarantees that all financial statements are organized on an accrual basis, presenting a comprehensive and accurate view of public area entities' economic positions and performances. This degree of reporting allows stakeholders—who include government officials, citizens, investors, and international partners—to make knowledgeable selections primarily based on dependable and similar economic facts. Furthermore, adhering to IPSAS promotes better economic management practices, reduces corruption and mismanagement, and enhances overall governance and the transport of public services. The finding suggests that the adoption of IPSAS extensively improves monetary management practices. This end result suggests that as public area entities implement IPSAS, they enjoy outstanding enhancements of their financial management practices. The high degree of settlement among respondents may also stem from the structured framework that IPSAS gives, which incorporates standardized financial reporting and greater responsibility. In conclusion, as public companies keep undertaking these standards, it is in all likelihood that they'll enjoy similarly enhancements of their operational efficiency and responsibility, in the end reaping rewards the wider public quarter area in Nigeria.

based on the findings concerning the effect of IPSAS on public zone entities in Anambra country, the and advocated that the Anambra state Ministry of Finance ought to put in force ongoing training applications for public area personnel on IPSAS compliance and fine practices in order to ensure that workforce are nicely-equipped to apply the standards correctly, thereby similarly enhancing economic management practices across all public entities.

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